

SYNTHESIS OF ALUMINUM AND MAGNESIUM RETAINING PHTHALOCYANINE PIGMENTS FOR THERMAL STABLE LOC PAINT PRODUCTS AND THEIR RESEARCH

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Abstract. Phthalic anhydride, Urea, metal salts and catalysts were synthesized in the most appropriate conditions. The technology of synthesizing aluminum-magnesium-preserving phthalocyanine pigments with a new composition has been developed economically and practically. Aluminum Magnesium Phthalocyanine pigments synthesized in our research work are characterized with differential thermogravimetric and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) analysis.

Keywords: aluminum oxide, magnesium acetate, phthalic anhydride, phthalocyanine, differential thermogravimetric, Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis

Introduction: The synthesis and research of high-temperature phthalocyanine pigments involves the preparation, characterization and application of phthalocyanine compounds that exhibit thermal stability and resistance to degradation at high temperatures. Phthalocyanine pigments are known for their intense color, chemical stability, and wide range of applications including paints, coatings, plastics, and inks. Improving their thermal stability expands their potential use in applications requiring high temperature exposure, such as automotive coatings, aerospace materials, and high-temperature industrial processes. [1].

- Phthalocyanines are usually synthesized by condensation reactions between phthalonitrile and metal salts in the presence of catalysts and high temperatures.

- Modifications to the phthalocyanine structure can be made during the synthesis process to provide resistance to high temperatures. These modifications may include the choice of metal ion (e.g. aluminum, cobalt, or nickel), functionalization of peripheral substituents, or introduction of heteroatoms into the phthalocyanine ring system [2].

Various analytical methods are used to characterize the synthesized phthalocyanine pigments. These may include spectroscopic techniques such as UV-Vis spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy (IR), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, and mass spectrometry (MS).

Thermal analysis methods such as thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) are used to evaluate the thermal stability and degradation behavior of pigments. [3]

Synthesized phthalocyanine pigments are subjected to thermal stability tests under controlled conditions, including prolonged exposure to high temperatures. [4,5]

In general, the synthesis and research of high-temperature phthalocyanine pigments involves a diverse approach, including synthetic chemistry, materials science, and performance testing. By developing pigments with enhanced thermal stability, researchers aim to expand the

range of applications of phthalocyanine-based colorants in demanding environments. [6,7] The high temperature resistance of aluminum magnesium-retaining phthalocyanine pigments synthesized by us was studied and elemental analysis was carried out. In addition, high-temperature-resistant phthalocyanin is used in coloring plastic products and increasing their resistance to external effects, stabilizers for polyethylene films, enamel preparation, printing inks, lok-paint drafts, dyeing cotton fabrics, and other areas. [8]

Main introduction: Aluminum magnesium-retaining phthalocyanine pigments were synthesized according to the most common method of obtaining metal phthalocyanine paints. Our synthesis was carried out in the presence of aluminum-magnesium-preserving phthalocyanine urea, phthalic anhydride, aluminum oxide and magnesium acetate catalyst. For synthesis at high temperature by the reaction heating method, a special container made of high-temperature, acid-resistant stainless steel with a capacity of 1000 ml, a high-temperature oven, glass pipe, rubber hose and materials are needed.

Substances:

Phthalic anhydride -----1 mol

Urea -----5 mol

Aluminum oxide -----0.25 mol

Magnesium acetate -----0.125 mol

Concentration of sulfuric acid (95%) 25 ml

Figure 1. Aluminum retaining phthalocyanine pigment with thermogravimetric (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA)

1 mol of phthalic anhydride, 5 mol of urea, 0.25 mol of aluminum oxide and 0.125 mol of magnesium acetate and 0.0005 mol of orthoboric acid were mixed. The resulting mixture was kept in an oven at 250 C for one hour. As a result of the reaction, gases and phthalimide begin to be released, which are unwanted substances that affect the production of pure products. Therefore, we install the exhaust pipe on the top of the furnace and immerse the hose connected to the pipe in a container of water, so that the exhaust gas does not affect the reaction and is safe. As a result,

a porous green substance was formed in the container. The resulting substance is cooled to 20°C and mixed with 20 ml of concentrated (95%) sulfuric acid.

After further purification and neutralization in the presence of the reaction, the composition of the green crystal indicates the formation of the product and is shown with Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and differential thermogravimetric analysis.

The analysis shows that the core mass loss in decay 1 is 25.34 -236.7°C for 22.18 min in which 46.494% of the core mass is lost. Decomposition 2 takes place at 236.70-408.34°C, during which 44.713% of the mass is lost. 3- decomposition takes place at 408.34-801.10°C, during which 4.626% of the mass is lost. The mass loss of the aluminum-magnesium-retaining phthalocyanine pigment over time due to temperature exposure is related to various processes: the mass increase due to the partial oxidation of the primary composites is observed. Decomposition begins in the composition, secondly, decomposition occurs with the release of volatile substances contained in the [5]. Magnesium-retaining phthalocyanine pigment, and decomposition accelerates due to the increase in temperature of other substances.

A detailed analysis of the thermogravimetric analysis curve and differential thermal analysis curve is given in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Effect of temperature on weight loss of aluminum and magnesium phthalocyanine

№	dw 3,48	1/T	dw/dt	M.r	Минт	T ⁰ +K
1	3.41	0.0026	0.008	0.07	8.38	373
2	2.77	0.0021	0.038	0.71	18.56	473
3	2.00	0.0017	0.051	1.48	28.6	573
4	1.31	0.0014	0.055	2.17	38.8	673
5	0.31	0.0012	0.064	3.17	48.8	773
6	0.24	0.0011	0.055	3.24	58.8	873
7	0.15	0.0010	0.047	3.33	69.9	973
8	0.14	0.0009	0.041	3.34	80.2	1073

The activation energy values for this process are shown for aluminum and magnesium phthalocyanine.

Table 2

Results of thermal-oxidation analysis of aluminum and magnesium phthalocyanine.

№	dw 3.48	Ln(W ₁ /W ₂)	1/T *10 ⁻³
1	3.41	0.020	2.6
2	2.77	0.228	2.1
3	2.00	0.553	1.7
4	1.31	0.977	1.4
5	0.31	2.418	1.2
6	0.24	2.674	1.1
7	0.15	3.144	1.0
8	0.14	3.213	0.9

Thus, on the basis of experimental data obtained on the kinetics of processes in the temperature range from 298.38 to 1074.78 K, the characteristics of thermal-oxidative degradation of aluminum and magnesium phthalocyanine were studied.

Figure 2. Scanning electron microscope view of aluminum-magnesium-retaining phthalocyanine pigment

The obtained analysis shows that the remains of unreacted initial substances are not visible in the images of aluminum-magnesium phthalocyanine pigments at 200, 700, and 1000 times magnification. The SEM image of aluminum-magnesium phthalocyanine pigments differs from other pigments. This makes it possible to obtain information about the completion of the reaction and, in parallel, about the element composition of the substance formed in the reaction. It showed aluminum magnesium-encapsulated phthalocyanine pigment nanoparticles ranging in size from 35.52 to ~47.25 nm. [6] At the same time, elemental analysis was carried out on a separate surface in large clusters. Large clusters were analyzed for elemental analysis and no excess elements were found at the points studied except for the aluminum magnesium-containing phthalocyanine pigment.

Table 3

Elemental analysis of aluminum magnesium phthalocyanine pigment

Element	Mass%	Atom %
C	49.00	55.00
N	21.28	20.48
O	27.43	23.12
Al	1.40	0.70
Mg	0.44	0.55
S	0.46	0.19
generally:	100.00	100.00

Based on the mentioned elemental analysis, the analysis of the elements in the pigment was shown in the form of a table in relation to 100 parts by mass.

Conclusion

In the course of research, the synthesis of phthalocyanine pigments containing aluminum-magnesium was successfully carried out. Various reaction conditions and optimal amounts of

substances were determined for the synthesis of these pigments. The purity of the pigments obtained during the reaction was analyzed. Synthesized aluminum-magnesium containing phthalocyanine pigments have been proven to have high thermal stability. These pigments retain their color and chemical structure even at high temperatures, which allows them to be used in various thermal conditions. Aluminum-magnesium-containing phthalocyanine pigments can be widely used in varnish and paint products, in the automotive industry, in the fields of architecture and construction, due to their thermal stability. These pigments have bright and attractive colors and play an important role in the aesthetic appearance of products and prolonging their service life. Synthesized pigments are ecologically safe, the process of their production and application does not harm the environment. This is important in the production of environmentally friendly products. Through the synthesis of aluminum-magnesium-containing phthalocyanine pigments and the research of their thermal stability properties, the possibility of creating high-quality, thermally and chemically stable lacquer paint products has increased. Pigments obtained as a result of these studies play an important role in the industrial and construction sectors, as well as in preserving the color of various products and materials for a long time.

REFERENCES

1. Fayziev J.B., Beknazarov X.S., Djalilov A.T. // Mis ftalotsianin pigmenti sintezi va uning iqspekterining tahlilini o'rganish // Namangan davlat Universiteti ilmiy axborotnomasi NamDU 2020. 3-son 125-128 bet
2. Fayziev J.B., Djalilov A.T. // Metall ftalotsianinlarning sinteziga haroratning ta'siri // Mejdunarodnaya konferentsiya «Innovatsionnoye razvitie neftegazovoy otralsi, sovremennaya energetika i ix aktualnye problemy» 26 may 2020 goda. Toshkent-2020. 343-344 bet
3. Karolin Grundke, Rodrigo C. Silva, Uinald R. Kitzmann, Katja Xaynts, Kleber T. de Oliveyra, Opatzgach Zn-ftalosiyaninlarni yaqin infraqizil fotokatalizatorlar sifatida ishlatish fotokimyoviy a-aminonitril sintezi. *Organik kimyo jurnali* **2022**,87(9), 5630-5642. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.joc.1c03101>
4. Trevor M. Grant, Viktoriya Makintayr, Jenya Vestfrid, Hasan Raboui, Robin T. Uayt, Zheng-Xong Lu, Benoit X. Lessard, Timoti P. Bender. Uch valentli va to'rt valentli guruh 13 va 14 ftalosiyaninlarning ftorid almashinuvi uchun to'g'ridan-to'g'ri va nisbatan xavfsiz jarayon. *ACS Omega* **2019**,4 (3) ,5317-5326. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.8b03202>.
5. [Файзиев, Жаҳонгир Баҳромович, Хасан Сойибназарович Бекназаров, and Абдулаҳат Турапович Джалилов. "Синтез и свойства фталоцианина меди." *Universum: технические науки* 3-2 \(72\) \(2020\): 69-71.](#)
6. Файзиев.Ж.Б «Таркибида металл сақловчи янги фталоцианин пигментларини олиш технологиясини ишлаб чиқиш» Тошкент 2021. Дисс.
7. Юсупов М.О., Бекназаров Х.С., Тиллаев А.Т., Джалилов А.Т// Янги таркибли кобалт фталоцианин пигментининг лок-бўёқ материаллар композициясидаги термоаналитик таҳлили// Композиционные материалы. Ташкент –2019. – № 3. – С.24-27.
8. Тожиқулов М., Файзиев Ж. «Термик барқарор фталоцианин комплекс синтези ик спектри таҳлили ва фталоцианин комплекси қўшилган алкид эмал бўёқнинг дериватограммаси таҳлили »// Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 14.